

BOARD ATTRIBUTES AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED INSURANCE FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Keyword:

Financial Performance, Nigeria Stock Exchange, Return on Assets (ROA), Human Capital Efficiency, Moderating Variable.

Abstract: *This study examined board attributes and financial performance of listed insurance firms on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The study objective was to investigate the effect between Board attributes (Board diligence, Board gender diversity and Remuneration committee) and financial performance (Return on assets) with human capital efficiency as a moderating variable of insurance firms in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. The study population was twenty five (25) listed insurance firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group. The sample size was eighteen (18) of the listed firms drawn using the census approach and based on availability. The data of the study was retrieved from annual reports of the listed companies for the period of 2013-2022. The statistical tool used was descriptive statistics, bivariate correlations, multiple regressions, robust standard error, and moderated multiple regressions analysis to establish the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. But negative effect on return on assets. Human capital efficiency significantly moderates the relationship between board attributes and return on assets. The study therefore concluded that gender diversity does not have a significant effect on the financial performance of insurance firms in Nigeria. The study recommended that firms should maintain remuneration committee, given the strong influence it has on financial performance. Remuneration committees should be independent and gender diversity should be enhanced.*

Introduction

In the past, businesses were largely managed by individuals; however, the evolving global landscape and the growing demands of

shareholders and stakeholders have necessitated a more structured and accountable approach to corporate operations. Central to this shift is the board of directors, whose composition and

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attributes significantly influence organizational governance and performance. As a result, the topic of board attributes and their impact on corporate governance and financial performance has gained considerable attention among researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Over the past decade, there has been a marked increase in research exploring various dimensions of corporate boards such as structure, diversity, and diligence and how these factors relate to firm outcomes (Okolie & Uwejean, 2022). The frequency of board meetings, commonly used to measure board diligence, has been positively linked to improved performance, as it provides more opportunities for strategic deliberation (Eluyela et al., 2018). Therefore, this paper seeks to examine the relationship between board attributes and financial performance of listed insurance firms on the Nigeria Stock Exchange.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of board attributes on financial performance, with evidence from insurance companies.

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of board gender diversity on return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the effect of remuneration committee on return of assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the effect of board diligence on return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

- iv. Evaluate the moderating effect of human capital efficiency on board attributes and return on assets of insurance firms in Nigeria.

Research questions

1. What is the effect of board gender diversity on return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of remuneration committee on return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria?
3. What is the effect of board diligence on return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria?
4. What the moderating effect of human capital efficiency is on board attributes and return on assets of insurance firms in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

From the above research questions, the following hypothesis were formulated:

1. Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.
2. Existence of remuneration committee does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.
3. Board diligence does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.
4. Human capital efficiency does not significantly moderate board attributes and return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of Board Attributes

Board attributes pertain to the diverse characteristics and qualities that shape the makeup, structure, and operations of a company's board of directors (Dagunduro, Dada & Asubiojo 2023). These features encompass a broad spectrum of factors, including the size, composition, diversity, independence, expertise, and experience of board members, as well as the roles and responsibilities they undertake. Essentially, board attributes encompass the traits and qualities of corporate boards that are accountable for overseeing the overall management of the firm.

Dimensions of Board Attributes

Board Gender Diversity

The relation between gender diversity and firm performance is an extensive concern of board composition and it has received growing attention recently from academics and policymakers. It is one of the most debatable and argued topic of the board's composition, especially on environmental and social issues.

According to Dutta and Bose (2007), the definition of gender diversity in the boardroom refers to the presence of women as the board of directors which is an important aspect of board diversity. Gender diversity could bring board functioning that eventually could influence firm performance.

Having a more gender-diverse workforce is not only the right thing to do from a societal perspective; it is also good for business. Research

illustrates that companies that effectively manage diversity and inclusion, achieve superior financial results and corporate performance. In 2016, for example, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) published a study of more than two million companies in Europe.

Remuneration Committee

Sari and Tjoe (2017) Remuneration of the board of directors and executives needs to be considered in corporate governance, because the level of remuneration must be designed in such a way as to be attractive enough to incentivize the board of directors and executives to run the company effectively. Thus, RCs play an important role in maintaining and controlling the board of directors and executives, where an effective RC can ensure that the remuneration structure (salary, honorarium, incentives, and allowances) of the board of directors and executives has been set to maximize performance, so that it will reduce agency costs and information asymmetry.

Board Diligence

Board diligence here refers to the number or frequency of board meetings. Board meetings are an important component of corporate governance as it provides an avenue for directors on the board to deliberate on issues and make strategic decisions that are germane to the success of a company and attainment of its overall objectives. According to Eluyela et al. (2018), regular board meetings is an internal issue at the discretion of chairman of board

meeting as there is no explicit governance law stipulating the minimum number of meetings.

Board members' frequency of meeting would bring about executing strategic objectives which could immensely increase the firm's performance. Frequency of meetings improved the Islamic banks' financial performance (Abubakar, Yahaya & Joshua 2023).

Concept of Financial Performance

Financial performance pertains to the measurement of a company's achievements and profitability based on its financial statements and key financial indicators (Nguyen et al., 2023). Analyzing financial performance involves assessing various financial metrics and ratios to acquire an understanding of a company's financial well-being and effectiveness. This assessment is crucial for investors, shareholders, lenders, and other stakeholders to make well-informed decisions (Dagunduro, Dada & Asubiojo, 2023).

Measure of Financial Performance

Return on Assets

Return on Asset is calculated by dividing company's annual earnings by its total assets. It is the ratio of annual net income to average total assets of a business in a financial year (Okpolosa, Chika & Promise 2022). The assets of the firm include both debt and equity used to fund firm's operation. This ratio measure for the operating efficiency for the company based on the firm's generated profits from its total assets. Return on Asset (ROA) is an indicator of the value of a firm's relative to its total assets. ROA gives an

idea as to how efficient management is at using its assets to generate earnings. ROA is displayed as a percentage. Sometimes this is referred to as "return on investment" For the purpose of this study, ROA is used to measure firms' financial performance.

Human Capital Efficiency

Human capital is considered the cornerstone for economic growth and development for any country (Tran & VO, 2020). Human capital can be useful for investors in assessing efficiency and predicting future profits and productivity. Human capital efficiency assesses the knowledge and skills of individuals, and that knowledge provides individuals with increased cognitive ability, leading them to be more efficient. It has also been refereed as the most important resources among all other resources (Boudlaie, Mahdiraji, Shamsi, Jafari-Sadeghi & Garcia-Perez 2020).

Theoretical Framework

Agency theory

This study uses the agency theory as a theoretical background to evaluate the board attributes. Agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976). They suggested a theory of how the governance of a company is based on the conflicts of interest between the company's owners (shareholders), and its managers. Companies directors serve as an agent to the owners, they work toward achieving companies' objective, and paid based on their performance and returns generated (Ahmed, Bahamman, & Abdulkarim 2020).

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Eluyela et al. (2018), the agents are appointed and corporate governance mechanisms instituted so as to ensure creation of a disciplined atmosphere, setting of timely and achievable strategic plan and the effective control of the management so as to maximize shareholders wealth via improved financial performance. An insurance firm which is publicly traded company whose shareholders are concerned with maximizing the value of their shares. The firm's managers, on the other hand, may have different objectives, such as maximizing their own compensation or maintaining their power within the company. This divergence of interests can lead to strategic decisions that are not optimal for the company or its shareholders. In this case, agency theory suggests that strong corporate governance can help align stakeholder interests and improve the firm's performance.

Agency theory assists us in understanding the monitoring role of board of directors in supervising and controlling management actions. Agency theorists argue that in order to protect the interests of shareholders, the board of directors must assume an effective oversight function. It is assumed that board performance of its monitoring duties is influenced by the effectiveness of the board, which in turn is influenced by factors such as board attributes...

According to agency theory, compensation contracts should be planned to align to the interests of managers (agents) with that of shareholders (principal). For example, the appointment of an independent and competent

board of directors to form a remuneration committee that will remunerate the directors without any form is in the interests of shareholders. Similarly, compensating executives based on company performance can provide an incentive to work hard to increase the value of the company (Ahmed et al., 2020). The remuneration committee variable is underpinned by agency theory because in line with the principle as the shareholder employs an independent remuneration committee as the agent to work on behalf of them, to remunerate its directors independently and appropriately without bias.

Stewardship theory

This theory is based on the assumption that the interests of shareholders and the interests of management are aligned; hence management is motivated to make decisions that would maximize the firm's performance and total value. Stewardship theory has its roots in psychology and sociology. The theory is based on the assumption that the interests of shareholders and the interests of management are aligned; hence management is motivated to take decisions that would maximize the firm's performance and total value. The theory advocates that there is greater utility in cooperative than individualistic behaviour (Donaldson & Davis, 1991); in that, managers maximize their utility functions, while maximizing shareholders' wealth (Davies, 1997). To achieve these, shareholders must authorize the appropriate empowering governance

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structure, mechanisms, authority, and information to facilitate the management autonomy, built on trust, to make decisions that would minimize their liability while achieving the firm's objectives (Donaldson & Dave, 1991). Thus, stewardship theory recognizes the need for executives to act more autonomously to maximize the shareholder's returns. Unlike agency theory, stewardship theory stresses the role of top management as stewards, expected to integrate their goals as part of the organization. This suggests that stewards are satisfied and motivated when organizational goals are attained. Davis (1997) identifies five components of the management philosophy of stewardship: trust, open communication, empowerment, long-term orientation, and performance enhancement. Daily (2023) argues that executives and directors are inclined to protect their reputations by ensuring that their organizations are properly operated to maximize financial performance. Shleifer & Vishny (1997) affirm that managers work to maximize investors' profit and to establish a good reputation to enable them to retain their positions. Stewardship theory also advocates unifying the role of the CEO and the chairman in order to reduce agency costs (Abdullah & Valentine, 2022). Finally, Donaldson & Davis (1991) show that combining both stewardship theory and agency theory improved firm performance, rather than separated. A stewardship protects and maximizes shareholders wealth through firm performance,

because by so doing the steward utility function are maximized. Davis, et al. (1997) and also cited in (Cullen, Kirwan & Brennan 2021).

Stewardship theory emphasizes the roles of management and expects it to see themselves as part of the firm to maximize the financial performance. Both agency and Stewardship theories discuss the relationship between the shareholders and management, while agency theory distinguishes ownership from control, stewardship theory is on the functions of management in the interest of shareholders. Stewardship theory did not give regard to other stakeholders but only emphasize the primary roles of management in the interest of the shareholders.

Empirical review

Setiani and Novitasari (2024) examined the influence of board attributes on ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) scores. The total sample is 86 companies from 2019 to 2023, resulting in 433 firm-year observations. The dependent variable is the standardized ESG Score; a high score indicates excellent relative ESG performance and a high degree of transparency in reporting material ESG data publicly. The independent variables used are the Sustainability Committee, Gender Diversity, and Board Meetings. The findings of this study indicate that certain board attributes, specifically the presence of a sustainability committee within the company, gender diversity among board members, and the average overall attendance percentage of board meetings, positively

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influence ESG Scores. Companies must pay attention to board attributes to improve their ESG Scores, encourage sustainable value creation, and foster stakeholder trust and confidence in their commitment to environmental, social, and governance excellence.

Saleh et al (2025), examined the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices and corporate risk in Asian countries, emphasizing the moderating role of board gender diversity (BGD). Using a panel dataset of 15,496 observations from Asian firms between 2008 and 2020, the analysis employs the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) model to address potential endogeneity issues. The findings indicate that stronger ESG practices significantly reduce corporate risk, enhance financial stability, and mitigate regulatory and market volatility exposure. Furthermore, the results highlight that higher BGD amplifies this risk-reduction effect, suggesting that diverse boards contribute to better decision-making and risk management. Policy Implications: These findings underscore the importance of regulatory frameworks that encourage ESG adoption and board diversity. Policymakers should incentivize companies to integrate ESG principles and implement gender diversity policies, such as board quotas or disclosure requirements, to enhance corporate resilience and sustainable economic growth.

Al-absy and Merza (2024) examined the influence of remuneration committee (RC)

characteristics, namely separation, size, independence, meetings, and female directors, on firm performance (FP) by using return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and earnings per shares (EPS). The study covers all firms being listed in Bahrain Bourse for two years which are 2020 and 2021. The results of the study show that having more directors in RC would significantly increase firm performance “ROE and EPS.” Further, having more females in RC would significantly increase firm performance “ROA.” In addition, having separate RC would significantly decrease firm performance “ROA and EPS.” Moreover, the independence of directors in RC and its frequent meetings has no significant impact on the firm’s performance. The results show that there is a need to re-evaluate the role of the RC and strengthen its effectiveness, as some of the variables examined by this study have an insignificant impact on a firm’s performance. Further, there is a need to allocate additional efforts and policies in developing corporate governance and RCs as well.

Methodology

Research Design

Research design is a set of procedures and methods used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the research problem. The design adopted in this study is the ex-post facto design. This design is suitable for this study because it involves the collection of data on annual reports of listed Insurance firms in the Nigeria Exchange Group.

The design seeks to identify antecedents of a present situation. The data collected from the annual reports were used to examine the effect of board attributes on financial performance of Insurance firms.

Population for the Study

A population is seen as an entire group of individuals, events or objects that possess similar characteristics (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Target population is referred to as a computed set of individuals, cases or objects with some observable characteristics of a particular nature that is different from other populations. A population according to Ngechu (2004) is a well-defined set of people, services, elements, and events, group of things or household being investigated. Population of interest must be homogenous. For the purpose of this study, the population consists of twenty five (25) Insurance companies in Nigeria. They are listed below:

- i. Alliance Insurance
- ii. Aiico Insurance
- iii. Axamansard Insurance
- iv. Consolidated Hallmark Insurance
- v. Continental Insurance
- vi. Cornerstone Insurance
- vii. Goldlink Insurance
- viii. Great Nigerian Insurance
- ix. Guinea Insurance
- x. International Energy Insurance
- xi. Lasaco Assurance
- xii. Law Union & Rock Insurance
- xiii. Linkage Assurance
- xiv. Mutual Benefits Assurance

- xv. N.E.M. Insurance
- xvi. Niger Insurance Co.
- xvii. Prestige Assurance Co.
- xviii. Regency Alliance Insurance
- xix. Sovereign Trust Assurance
- xx. Standard Alliance Insurance
- xxi. Standard Trust Assurance
- xxii. SUNU Assurances Nigeria
- xxiii. Universal Insurance Company
- xxiv. Verita Kapital Assurance
- xxv. Coronation Insurance

The information above was sourced from the financial services sector section in the 2019/2020 fact book of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE, 2020)

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

To ascertain our sample of this study, the following factors were considered.

- I. The insurance firm must not have been delisted within the period covered by this study as to ensure data availability.
- II. Data to be sourced from the Nigeria exchange group for the period under review must be complete and accessible.

So, census approach sampling technique was used from a population of 25 insurance companies, based on availability and reliability of data, 18 insurance firms were chosen as the sample.

Table 3.1. Sample size of the study

1. African Alliance Plc
2. Aiico Insurance Plc
3. Axa Mansard Insurance Plc
4. Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc

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5. Continental Reinsurance Plc
6. Cornerstone Insurance Plc
7. Coronation Insurance Plc
8. Goldlink Insurance Plc
9. International Energy Plc
10. Lasaco Assurance Plc
11. Linkage Assurance Plc
12. Mutual Benefits Assurance Plc
13. N.E.M. Insurance Plc
14. Prestige Assurance Plc
15. Regency Alliance Plc
16. Sovereign Trust Plc
17. SUNU Assurance Plc
18. Veritas Kapital Assurance Plc

Sources of Data

The data was sourced from the published annual reports of the listed insurance firms that are in NGX from 2013-2022. This is justified because it covers the International Financial reporting Standards (IFRS) period. The secondary method data collection was adopted as it is considered more reliable and in line with the quantitative design. Availability of all required data for computation of board attributes and financial performance of listed Nigerian insurance firms also means that measurement procedure can be

Table 1. Measurement of Study Summary

S/n	Variables	Definition	Type	Measure	Source
1	BGD	Board Gender Diversity	Independent	Proportion of females directors in the board	Pandey et al. (2023), Kabir et al. (2023)

easily verified, hence the choice over primary data.

Measurement of the Study

The variables that were adopted to measure the effect of board attributes on financial performance of listed insurance firms in Nigeria are presented in the section.

Financial performance variables (Dependent variables)

- Return on Assets (ROA): This is measured by net profit divided by total assets.
- Board Diligence (BOD): This is measured by the number of meetings the board of directors hold in the year.
- Board Gender Diversity (BGD): This is measured by the ratio of females to the board of directors.
- Remuneration Committee (REM): Data was generated simply by, 'Is there a Remuneration committee?' So, the value of dummy REM is 1 if the answer is YES and 0, if it is NO.

Moderating Variables

- Human Capital Efficiency (HCE): This is measured by dividing value added by human capital (staff) costs.

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2	REM	Remuneration Committee	Independent	A dummy variable, generated by, ‘Is there a Remuneration committee?’ Value is 1 if the answer is YES and 0, if it is NO.	Yahaya (2022), Al-absy and Merza (2024)
3	BOD	Board Diligence	Independent	Number of board meetings in a year	Ajide et al. (2022), Appah and Tebepah (2023)
4	ROA	Return on Assets	Dependent	The net profit divided by total assets.	Al-absy and Merza (2024), Egbunike et al. (2023)
5	HCE	Human Capital Efficiency	Moderating	Dividing Value added by human capital (staff) costs.	Mohammad (2023), Agbi et al. (2022)

Model Specifications

In order to test the effect of board attributes on financial performance of listed insurance firms in Nigeria from 2013 – 2022, this study adopted a linear model.

Model 1: Return on asset model (ROA) Model

$$ROA = f(BOD, REM, BGD) \dots \dots \dots 3.1$$

This can be written in Ordinary Least Square (OLS) form as:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{it} + \beta_2 BOD_{it} + \beta_3 REM_{it} + \beta_5 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \text{Model 1}$$

Where: ROA= Return on asset, a proxy for financial performance

BOD= Board diligence, a proxy for board attributes

REM= Remuneration committee, a proxy for board attributes

BGD= Board gender diversity, a proxy for board attributes

It= time period under study

β_0 = constant

β_1 - β_5 = coefficient of explanatory variables

ϵ = error item

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Model 2: Moderated multiple regression model with ROA As dependent variable

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{it} + \beta_2 REM_{it} + \beta_3 BOD_{it} + \beta_4 HCE_{it} + \beta_5 BGD * HCE_{it} + \beta_6 REM * HCE_{it} + \beta_7 BOD * HCE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

This can be written in OLS form as:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BGD_{it} + \beta_2 REM_{it} + \beta_3 BOD_{it} + \beta_4 HCE_{it} + \beta_5 BGD * HCE_{it} + \beta_6 REM * HCE_{it} + \beta_7 BOD * HCE_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where: ROA= return on assets

BGD= board gender diversity

REM= remuneration committee

BOD= board diligence

HCE= human capital efficiency

BGD*HCE= interaction term between board gender diversity and human capital efficiency

REM*HCE=interaction term between remuneration committee and human capital efficiency

BOD*HCE= interaction term between board diligence and human capital efficiency

It= time period under study

β0= constant

B1-β7= coefficient of explanatory variables

e= error item

Method of Data Analysis

This study adopted the multiple regression analysis to establish the effect of board attributes on the financial performance of listed insurance firms, from 2013 – 2022, using the identified variables.

Other tests of significance, which were used in the study, are:

i.R²= coefficient of determination was used to test the explanatory power of the independent variables.

ii.T-test was used to test for the significance of the coefficient of the variables

iii.F-ratio was used to test for the significance of the overall model

iv.Durbin –Watson (DW) was used test whether auto-correlation exist or not in error term (e)

This study used SPSS package to facilitate the process of estimation of the models relating board attributes and Financial Performance of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data Presentation

The data used for this study were obtained from the corporate information section of the published annual reports of the insurance firms, the constituted sample for this study. Data obtained from this section were in respect of board gender diversity, remuneration committee and board diligence. Data on return on assets, leverage, capital adequacy, and firm size were obtained from the statement of financial position, while the data on human capital efficiency were obtained from the statement of value added. Please refer to appendix 1 for the data.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1. Below presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study.

Table 4.1. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation
BGD	180	0	0.6	0.1933	0.13667
REM	180	0	1	0.4	0.49126
BOD	180	3	15	5.3778	1.64149
ROA	180	-0.69	0.16	0.0046	0.11529
LEV	180	0.12	5.53	0.7982	0.96204
CAD	180	-4.53	0.88	0.2018	0.96204
HCE	180	-6.7	6.08	2.122	1.53803
FS	180	14.4	23.64	17.115	1.70979

Source: Descriptive statistics from SPSS output
The variables used in the study are board gender diversity (BGD), remuneration committee (REM), board diligence (BOD), return on assets (ROA), and while human capital efficiency (HCE) is the moderating variable. The independent variables are BGD, REM and BOD, while ROA are the dependent variables.

Descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in Table 4.1. As shown by the table, there are 180 observations in the study made up of data from eighteen (18) insurance firms over a period of ten (10) years.

The minimum value for board gender diversity (BGD) is zero, suggesting that in at least one insurance firm, there was no female in the board of directors. The maximum value of 0.6, suggests that in at least one insurance firm, female representation in the board was as high as sixty percent (60%), indicating that insurance firms in Nigeria are gender friendly.

The minimum value for remuneration committee is zero (0) indicating the non-

existence of remuneration committee, and the maximum value of one (1) indicating the existence of the committee. The mean value of 0.4 indicates that at least 40% of insurance firms in Nigeria have a remuneration committee.

Board diligence has a minimum of 3 and a maximum of 15, indicating that the frequency of board meetings was as low as three (3) times per year, and as high as fifteen (15) times per year, in at least one insurance firm. The mean value of 5.3 indicates that on the average, board members meet five (5) times in the insurance industry in Nigeria.

The minimum value for return on assets (ROA) is -0.69 while the maximum value is 0.16. These values suggest that profitability in the insurance industry in Nigeria is low. This fact is supported by the low mean value of ROA (0.0046).

Human capital adequacy varied from a minimum value of -6.7 and a maximum value of 6.08, indicating that the efficiency in the use of human capital is high in some firms and low in other firms.

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4.3. Bivariate Analysis

		BGD	REM	BOD	ROA	HCE
BGD	Corr	1	-0.004	.177*	-.169*	-.171*
	Sig		0.959	0.017	0.024	0.021
REM	Corr	-0.004	1	0.047	-0.08	0.124
	Sig	0.959		0.53	0.285	0.096
BOD	Corr	.177*	0.047	1	-.369**	-.208**
	Sig	0.017	0.53		0.000	0.005
ROA	Corr	-.169*	-0.08	-.369**	1	.575**
	Sig	0.024	0.285	0		0.000
	Sig	0.533	0	0.032	0	0
HCE	Corr	-.171*	0.124	-.208**	.575**	1
	Sig	0.021	0.096	0.005	0	
FS	Corr	0.089	0.078	0.034	.306**	.150*
	Sig	0.234	0.299	0.649	0	0.045

Table 4.2 presents the Pearson correlation of the variables in the study. The highest correlation coefficient is 0.649, this is not up to 70%. It is suggested that correlations beyond this

threshold may suggest multicollinearity (Besley et al., 1980). Given the relatively low correlation coefficients of the independent variables, there is no serious issue of multicollinearity.

4.4. Multivariate Analysis

Table 4.3. Model Summary for Model 1

Model	R	R Sq	Adj R Sq	Std. Err	R. Sq Change	F Change	Sig. Change	F	Durbin-Watson
1	0.70	0.49	0.475	0.08351	0.49	33.432	0.000		1.605
a. Predictors:(Constant),FS,BOD,REM,BGD,CAD									
b. Dependent Variable: ROA									

This section presents the results of the multivariate analysis used in testing the hypotheses formulated for this study. Tables 4.3 to 4.5 are the results from multiple regression analysis for model 1. Table 4.3 presents the

model summary for model 1. The table shows that the independent variables explain approximately fifty percent (50%) of the variations in the ROA (the dependent variable). The model fits the data reasonably as the F value

is significant at the 1% level. The Durbin Watson statistics of 1.602 indicate that there is no problem of autocorrelation in the data set.

Table 4.4. ANOVA for model 1

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.166	5	0.233	33.432	.000b
	Residual	1.213	174	0.007		
	Total	2.379	179			
a Dependent Variable: ROA						
b Predictors: (Constant), FS, BOD, REM, BGD						

Table 4.4 presents the analysis of variance for the model 1. The regression sum of squares show that 49% of the total sum of squares is accounted

for by the independent variables. The F value of 33.432 is significant at the 1% level.

Table 4.5 Coefficients from Model 1 based on Robust Standard Errors

					Number of obs	=	180
					F(4, 1751)	=	7.44
					Prob > F	=	0.000
					R – squared	=	0.490
					Root MSE	=	.8035
ROA	Coeff.	Robust Std. Err	t	P> t	(95% conf. interval)		VIF
BGD	-0888	.0654	-1.36	0.176	-.21791	.04028	1.045
REM	.0168	.0120	1.40	0.164	-.00696	.04066	1.125
BOD	-.0188	.0077	-2.44	0.016	-.03420	-.00359	1.065
FS	.0079	.0022	3.55	0.000	.00352	.01235	1.227
cons	-.0325	.0349	-0.93	0.352	-.10153	-.10153	

Table 4.5 presents the table of coefficients for model 1. The variance inflation factor (VIF) range from 1.045 to 1.337, indicating absence of collinearity. The Table is based on Newey-west robust standard errors. According to Long and

Ervin (2000), the coefficients from regression based on robust standard errors overcomes regression violations, such as autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity.

Test of Hypothesis One

Hypothesis one states as follows:

HO₁: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of board gender diversity (BGD) is negative and not significant with a p value of 0.176. Given the alpha level of 0.05, the p value of 0.176 indicates that the coefficient is not significant. Accordingly, the results show that board gender diversity (BGD) has a significant negative but insignificant effect on ROA. Thus, hypothesis one is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis two states as follows:

HO₂: Existence of remuneration committee does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of remuneration committee (REM) is positive but not significant With a p value of 0.164. Since the p value of the coefficient of REM is far greater than 0.05,

Table 4.6. Model Summary for Model 2

Model	R	R Sq	Adj. R Square	Std. Error	R. Squ Change	F Change	Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
1	.502a	0.252	0.235	0.84132	0.252	14.763	0.000	0.266
a. Predictors: (Constant), FS, BOD, REM, BGD								
b. Dependent Variable: LEV								

Table 4.6 presents the model summary for model 2. The model shows that the independent variables explain more than twenty percent (20%) of variations in the dependent variable, and the model fits the data reasonably well. The Durbin-Watson statistics, however, shows that

It means the coefficient is not significant. Therefore, hypothesis two is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Hypothesis three states as follows:

HO₃: Board diligence does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of board diligence (BOD) is negative but significant with a p value equal to 0.016. This means that the hypothesis is rejected as board diligence has a significant (negative) effect on return on assets. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Table 4.5 further shows that the two control variables in the model (capital adequacy (CA) and firm size (FS)) each have a positive effect on return on assets. Indicating that the higher the value of either of them, the better the financial performance of the listed insurance firm (measured by ROA).

the data set suffers from autocorrelation. To overcome this regression violation, the Table of Coefficients (Table 4.8) which is used in the test of hypotheses four to six is based on Newey-

West Robust Standard errors which is autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity consistent.

Table 4.7. ANOVA for Model 2

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	41.799	4	10.45	14.763	.000b
	Residual	123.87	175	0.708		
	Total	165.669	179			

a. Dependent Variable: LEV
 b. Predictors: (Constant), FS, BOD, REM, BGD

Table 4.7 presents the analysis of variance for model 2. The results show an F score of 14.763,

which is significant at the 1% level. This means that the model fits the data reasonably well.

Table 4.8 Coefficients from model 2 based on Robust Standard Errors

					Number of obs	=	180
					F(4, 1751)	=	6.81
					Prob > F	=	0.000
					R – squared	=	0.252
					Root MSE	=	.8413
Lev	Coeff	Robust Std. Err	T	P> t	(95% conf. interval)		VIF
BGD	.4009	.4176	0.96	0.338	-.4232111	1.225171	1.045
REM	.5768	.1587	3.63	0.000	.2635322	.8901451	1.008
BOD	.0878	.0410	2.14	0.034	.0067829	.1689832	1.035
FS	-.224	.0598	-3.75	0.000	-.3425334	-.1064711	1.015
cons	3.859	1.039	3.71	0.000	1.808541	5.91081	

Source: Output from STATA

Table 4.8 presents the coefficients for model 2. The variance inflation factor (VIF) which tests collinearity, indicates that VIF values range from 1.008 to 1.05. These figures are far from the cut off value of 10. Thus, there is no problem of

collinearity in the data set used for the study. The Table is also from Newey-West robust standard error. This regression technique was adopted to overcome the problem of autocorrelation in the data set as shown by Table 4.6. The coefficients

therefore provide valid (not spurious) regression results.

4.5. Test of Moderation-effect

Table 4.9 Model Summary from Model 3

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		Sig. F Change
					R2 Change	F Change	
1	.643a	0.414	0.401	0.08926	0.414	30.91	0
2	.710b	0.504	0.484	0.08279	0.09	10.467	0
a Predictors: (Constant), HC, REM, BGD, BOD							
b Predictors: (Constant), HC, REM, BGD, BOD, REMHC, BGDHC, BODHC							
c Dependent Variable: ROA							

Table 4.9 presents the model summary from model 3 which seeks to determine the moderating effect of human capital efficiency in the relationship between board attributes and return on assets. Hypothesis seven (which addresses this relationship) is framed as follows: HO₄: Human capital efficiency does not significantly moderate the relationship between board attributes and return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In table 4.9, the model summary for model 3, the r square changed from 0.414 to 0.504. The change is significant at the 1% level. The two models in Table 4.9 were derived using the two stage regression approach in SPSS. The significant change shows that the moderating variable (human capital efficiency, HCE) has a moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and return on assets. The sign on the coefficients in Table 4.10 gives a clear indication that the change is positive.

Table 4.10. Coefficients from Model 3

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	0.03	0.028		1.082	0.281
	BGD	-0.029	0.05	-0.034	-0.571	0.569
	REM	-0.032	0.014	-0.135	-2.313	0.022
	BOD	-0.017	0.004	-0.245	-4.085	0
	HC	0.04	0.005	0.535	8.863	0

2	(Constant)	0.102	0.04		2.561	0.011
	BGD	-0.006	0.074	-0.007	-0.08	0.936
	REM	-0.068	0.025	-0.288	-2.713	0.007
	BOD	-0.028	0.005	-0.405	-5.92	0
	HC	-0.017	0.017	-0.221	-0.977	0.33
	BGDHC	-0.043	0.029	-0.193	-1.476	0.142
	REMHC	0.019	0.009	0.255	2.055	0.041
	BODHC	0.011	0.002	0.824	4.722	0

a Dependent Variable: ROA

Table 4.10 shows the table of coefficient for model 3. The first section on the table shows that HCE has a positive significant effect on ROA. In the second section of the table, REMHC (the interaction term for remuneration committee and human capital efficiency) and BODHC (the interactive term for board diligence and human capital efficiency), each has a positive and significant effect on ROA. The two variables

obviously contributed to the overall positive and significant moderating effect of human capital efficiency on the relationship between board attributes and return on assets. By these results, hypotheses seven is rejected as human capital efficiency has a positive and significant moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and ROA.

Table 4.11 Model Summary for Model 4

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error	Change Statistics		Sig. Change	F
					R2 square	F change		
1	.455a	0.207	0.189	0.8666	0.207	11.399	0.000	
2	.513b	0.263	0.233	0.84263	0.056	4.367	0.005	

a Predictors: (Constant), HC, REM, BGD, BOD

b Predictors: (Constant), HC, REM, BGD, BOD, REMHC, BGDHC, BODHC

c Dependent Variable: LEV

The model summary for model 4 is used to test hypothesis eight which states as follows:

HO8: Human capital efficiency does not significantly moderate the relationship between

board attributes and leverage of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

The model summary for model four was derived from the two stage regression approach in SPSS. The model shows that R square changed from

0.207 to 0.263 (a change of 0.056), and the change was significant at the 1% level ($p= 0.005$). This shows that human capital efficiency had a significant moderating effect on the relationship

between board attributes and leverage in the insurance industry in Nigeria, therefore, hypothesis 8 is rejected.

Table 4.12 Coefficients for Model 4

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	0.806	0.272		2.964	0.003
	BGD	-0.179	0.486	-0.025	-0.368	0.713
	REM	0.607	0.133	0.31	4.553	0.000
	BOD	0.046	0.041	0.078	1.116	0.266
	HC	-0.218	0.044	-0.348	-4.955	0.000
2	(Constant)	0.31	0.404		0.768	0.443
	BGD	0.19	0.748	0.027	0.255	0.799
	REM	1.192	0.254	0.609	4.694	0.000
	BOD	0.078	0.049	0.133	1.587	0.114
	HC	0.1	0.172	0.16	0.582	0.561
	BGDHC	0.072	0.299	0.038	0.24	0.81
	REMHC	-0.274	0.095	-0.435	-2.877	0.005
	BODHC	-0.039	0.023	-0.356	-1.675	0.096
a Dependent Variable: LEV						

Table 4.12 is the table of coefficients for Model \$, the model that seeks to test the moderating effect of human capital efficiency on the relationship between board attributes and leverage in the insurance industry in Nigeria.

The first part of the model showed that human capital efficiency (HCE) had a negative coefficient which was significant at the 1% level. In the second part of the table, of the three interaction terms two of them (REMHC and BODHC) were significant. These two variables

had negative coefficients. Put together, the results showed that human capital efficiency significantly moderated the relationship between board attributes and leverage, but the direction of the moderation is negative.

4.6. Test of Hypotheses

HO₁: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of board gender diversity (BGD) is negative and barely significant

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with a p value of 0.059. Given the alpha level of 0.05 it is possible to regard 0.059 as a value that is approximately equal to 0.05. Accordingly, the results show that board gender diversity (BGD) has a significant negative effect on ROA. Thus, hypothesis is rejected.

HO₂: Existence of remuneration committee does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of remuneration committee (REM) is positive but not significant With a p value of 0.213. Since the p value of the coefficient of REM is far greater than 0.05,

It means the coefficient is not significant. Therefore, hypothesis two is accepted.

HO₃: Board diligence does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In Table 4.5, the coefficient of board diligence (BOD) is negative but significant with a p value equal to 0.000. This means that the hypothesis is rejected as board diligence has a significant

negative effect on return on assets. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is rejected.

In Table 4.8, the coefficient of remuneration committee (REM) is positive with a t-statistic score of 4.487. The p value of 0.000 indicates the coefficient of REM is significant at 1% level. Accordingly, hypothesis 5 is rejected.

HO₄: Human capital efficiency does not significantly moderate the relationship between board attributes and return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.

In table 4.9, the model summary for model 3, the r square changed from 0.414 to 0.504. The change is significant at the 1% level. The two models in Table 4.9 were derived using the two stage regression approach in SPSS. The significant change shows that the moderating variable (human capital efficiency, HCE) has a moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and return on assets. The sign on the coefficients in Table 4.10 gives a clear indication that the change is positive.

Table 4.13. Summary of Hypothesis Tested

H ₀	Hypotheses	P Value	Significance	Decision
1	Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.	0.176	Negatively Insignificant	Accepted
2	Existence of remuneration committee does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.	0.164	Positively Insignificant	Accepted

3	Board diligence does not significantly affect the return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.	0.016	Negatively Significant	Rejected
4	Human capital efficiency does not significantly moderate the relationship between board attributes and return on assets of listed insurance firms in Nigeria.	0.000	Positively Significant	Rejected

4.7. Discussion of Findings

Board Gender Diversity and Return on Assets

Board gender diversity (BGD) indicated a negatively insignificant relationship with return on assets (ROA) of listed insurance firms in Nigeria, implying that board gender diversity does not influence profitability as regards to ROA, This is in line with the study of Otonne et al. (2023) and Pandey et al. (2023), as they found that board gender diversity does not affect ROA. They both concluded that women on the board adversely affects financial performance.

Pandey et al. (2023) added that that board gender diversity does not affect firm financial performance in isolation, but rather in combination with other board and firm characteristics.

This study agrees with that, as when interacted with human capital efficiency (HCE), BGD i.e. BGD*HCE, it had a positive significant relationship with ROA.

Remuneration Committee and Return on Assets

Remuneration committee (REM) and return on assets (ROA) of listed insurance firms in Nigeria indicated a positively insignificant relationship in this current study. This means the effect of remuneration committee is a positive one but not strong enough to influence the return on asset. This is in contrary with Al-absy and Merza (2024) study which found that the existence of remuneration is positively and significantly related to financial performance at 10% level of significance. Yahaya (2022) also found and indicated a significantly positive relationship between the remuneration committee and profitability. The disparity in the results since it’s positively insignificant might be due to the non-independence of the remuneration committee members, as some have been observed to be board directors in the listed insurance firms.

Board Diligence and Return on Assets

Board diligence (BOD) has a significant negative effect on return on assets (ROA) of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. This is in line with

Ajide et al. (2022) who also found a significant negative relationship between board diligence and profitability. Kyei et al. (2022) also concluded that more board meetings reduce banks' performance in sub-Saharan Africa. Their results suggested that fewer board meeting enhances the shareholder value of Banks in Sub-Saharan Africa but not their counterparts in North Africa. Our findings mean that board directors of listed insurance firms that meet less regularly have been found to perform better and improve the profitability of insurance firms. In fact, frequency of board meeting is a corporate red flag according to our findings.

Human capital efficiency and Return on Assets

Human capital efficiency (HCE) has a significantly positive moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and return on assets (ROA) in this study. This is similar to the findings of Mohammad (2023) who found that human capital efficiency and ROE have significant effects, and in line with the findings of Agbi et al. (2022) who revealed that HCE had significant positive effect on ROA. Based on this, the study concludes that human capital efficiency is very vital in determining the profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. This means that, the higher the human capital efficiency in a listed insurance firm in Nigeria, even in the presence of weak board attributes, the influence is strong enough to get a better and more positive financial performance.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Following the frequent poor financial performance in the Nigerian insurance industry and in order to mitigate the conflict of interest that stems from the separation between corporate ownership and control, a couple of academics suggested corporate governance mechanisms as the conflict resolution. It is strongly suggested that appropriate preparation of appropriate board attributes can guard firm's weaknesses. To this effect, three measures of board attributes were selected and put to test their effect on financial performance (which was measured by two variables).

So, this study examined the effect of board attributes on financial performance of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. The study looked into the impact of board diligence (BOD), board gender diversity (BGD) and remuneration committee (REM) of the selected listed insurance firms on performance and measures of return on assets (ROA). The study employed ex post facto research design and secondary source of data collection which was obtained from the Nigeria exchange group (NGX) fact book and annual report of the companies. The findings of the study as follows:

1. Board gender diversity is negatively related to return on assets of listed Nigerian insurance firms, and the relationship is insignificant.

2. Remuneration committee is positively related to return on assets of listed Nigerian insurance firms, and it is insignificant.

3. Board diligence has a significant negative effect on return on assets of listed Nigerian insurance firms.

4. Human capital efficiency has a positively significant moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and return on assets.

Conclusion

The study conducted an empirical investigation to ascertain the effect of board attributes on the financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria using time series data are cross sectional in nature covering a period of 10 years, which is between 2013-2022. The sample of the study consisted of eighteen (18) listed insurance companies on the Nigerian exchange group. It used secondary data sourced from annual reports of the sampled insurance firms. The study employed two theories which are Agency theory and resource dependency theory. It formulated eight null hypotheses and tested them using multiple regression analysis and moderated multiple analysis with the aid of SPSS software. The study showed that board attributes have mixed effects on the selected proxies of financial performance of the sampled listed insurance firms in Nigeria. The study concluded that board diligence and remuneration committee has stronger effect than board gender diversity. The study also concluded that human capital efficiency has a significant relationship with the financial performance of insurance

firms in Nigeria, the conclusion was consistent, whether financial performance is being measured by return on assets or leverage, so it had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and financial performance of insurance firms in Nigeria.

Recommendations

In line with the findings and conclusions of the study. The following recommendations are being made:

1. Very frequent board meetings can be a waste of resources, so an average of 5 board meetings in listed Nigerian firms is advised, given that it reflects a significant positive role in the financial performance. This is because board meetings reflect the health and sustainability of the firm, which is important for effective company's management and profitability.

2. Insurance firms without the existence of remuneration committee, should consider it. Most importantly, it should consist of more independent and non-executive directors in order to make remuneration policies that protect the interest of the shareholders.

3. Gender diversity of the board should be line with professional requirements and qualifications, aside being considered as a competitive advantage that leads to societal validation. Also, listed insurance firms should consider the need to admit more female board members to balance up the ratio of board gender diversity. This will have a more significant effect and create a more resourceful board in terms of

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risk evaluation, which serves as a check to profitability and solvency.

4. Regulatory bodies of the Insurance firms in Nigeria should emphasize on all board attributes and make sure of its effectiveness in order to enhance the general financial performance of the insurance industry. Profitability is most times associated with leverage, so, insurance firms should pit more focus on their assets and explore their leverage, they define the firm's health and it will lead to greater financial performances, reflecting on both their ROA and leverage.

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